

Detection of Firewalling to Professionalize Attacks

Marc Ruef

Research Department, scip AG

maru@scip.ch

<https://www.scip.ch>

Keywords: Block, Detect, Dienstleistung, Firewall, ICMP, Nmap, Portscan, Risk

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2015 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150416> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

During our *security checks* [1] it's not unusual that auditors, clients and partners discuss vulnerabilities and risks. This discussion, assuming that it is civil and all people involved respect each other, is of great importance. Because during those discussions, the quality of the project itself as well as the overall understanding of the subject of information security will be talked about.

Some of our clients are less versed in recognizing the real-life risks of an attack scenario. Sometimes, the technical understanding of the attack mechanism is lacking. Other times, it's the understanding of the *psychology of an attacker* [2].

As an example: When we find reason to believe that a firewall component is used during one of our network analyses, then we might classify this as a medium finding. Medium means that the vulnerability presents a means for an attacker to gain advantages in preparing and conducting an attack.

There are typical indicators in network traffic that hint at the use of a packet filter:

- **Discarded Packets:** Using DROP, undesired packets are discarded without informing the sender about the rule infraction. Usually, systems using no firewall functionality deploy a DENY rule. The packet is dropped *and* the sender is informed about the infraction. This usually happens with a TCP segment with set RST flag or an ICMP unreachable packet. In nmap, ports are thus *labelled* [3] as CLOSED and not as FILTERED. If the switch `--reason` is enabled, the state identified will be explained.

- **Incrementing the TTL value:** The time to live field in an IPv4 packet is, according to *RFC 791* [4], is being decremented by 1 when it's passed through a routing element. Or when it remains on one for longer than a second. Firewall systems are basically routing elements and have to follow that rule. Using route tracing, inline elements can be recognized as such. This is usually attempted by using UDP or ICMP, but it can be done using the much less popular TCP.

```
maru@debian:~$ nmap scanme.insecure.org --reason
Starting Nmap 6.40 ( http://nmap.org ) at 2015-03-16 14:33 CET
Nmap scan report for scanme.insecure.org (74.207.244.221)
Host is up, received syn-ack (1.5s latency).
rDNS record for 74.207.244.221: scanme.nmap.org
Not shown: 991 closed ports
Reason: 991 conn-refused
PORT      STATE SERVICE REASON
22/tcp    open  ssh    syn-ack
25/tcp    open  smtp   syn-ack
80/tcp    open  http   syn-ack
110/tcp   open  pop3   syn-ack
119/tcp   open  nntp   syn-ack
143/tcp   open  imap   syn-ack
514/tcp   filtered shell  no-response
587/tcp   open  submission syn-ack
9929/tcp  open  nping-echo syn-ack

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 118.98 seconds
```


Figure: Nmap detects a filtered port

Where is this risk that comes from using this seemingly marginal information? As an attacker, it's important to know that the target environment is using security component, which mechanisms are deployed and predicting how those mechanisms react. In case a packet filter can be identified, it's reasonable to assume that certain communication is limited and certain activities are protocolled or that they cause an alert. Therefore, a highly professional attacker is keen on adapting various means, mainly the following:

- **Reduce timing** in order to avoid restriction and discovery. The data rate should be as high as possible in order to maintain the best possible efficiency, but it also shouldn't trigger any alarms. An outline of the standard settings of certain firewall products can be found in the article *Timing für effiziente unentdeckte Portscans* [5].

- **Define choice of ports** in order to gain elevated access. Typically, port 53 as target and source port is not filtered because it is used for DNS. Many an installation does *not* recognize a portscan with the source tcp/53. In other places, access with target port tcp/80 is *always* permitted.
- **Change attack patterns** in order to circumvent IDS and IPS solutions. The article *HP Tipping Point – Analysis of the Protection Filters* [6] discusses the standard setting as found in a popular network based IPS. In the article, there are a number of attack patterns that are typically not recognized. Preferring exotic portscan techniques can be a distinct advantage. As does the use of *fragmenting or dedicated options* [7].

The example of the packet filter in this article is just that, an example. Similar effects are observable in other seemingly *unimportant* analyses.

It's part of an operator's responsibility to mask the use of security mechanisms to shield them from detection or to at least make finding them difficult. This robs highly professional attackers of the possibility to adjust to their target environment easily. The chances that the mechanisms go undetected and therefore block intruders get higher. This should be the immediate goal for vulnerabilities that, at first glance, seem to be nothing but a minor risk. Every improvement in an environment is of advantage to its operators.

3. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?dienstleistungen.auditing>
- [2] <https://www.computec.ch/download.php?view.110>
- [3] <http://nmap.org/book/man-port-scanning-basics.html>
- [4] <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc791.txt>
- [5] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20130411>
- [6] <en/?labs.20131211>
- [7] <http://nmap.org/book/man-bypass-firewalls-ids.html>